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Evaluating the Potential of Gridded Precipitation Datasets for Reproducing Streamflow in a Mountainous Basin

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Abstract

Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) with high spatio-temporal resolution and large areal coverage have provided hydrologists a potential alternative source for hydrological applications in the recent decades. High altitude and complex terrain of eastern Turkey have been a great challenge for gauge-based precipitation observation for years. Hence, the objective of this study is to evaluate the potential of six Gridded Precipitation Datasets (CHIRPSv2.0, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv06, IMERGHHLv06, PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS) for reproducing the streamflow over a mountainous basin at daily time step. Two types of validation efforts for Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) are undertaken: (1) direct comparison of GPDs with observed precipitation data using Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE) including its three components (correlation, bias and variability ratio) are utilized. Moreover, three categorial metrics such as probability of detection (POD), false alarm ratio (FAR) and critical success index (CSI) are considered to evaluate the detectability strength of selected GPDs for different precipitation intensities; (2) evaluation of GPD ability for streamflow prediction using a conceptual hydrologic model under Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE) and Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) metrics. For the GPD direct validation, CHIRPSv2.0 shows the highest performance (KGE; 0.15), followed by CHIRPv2.0 and IMERGHHLv06 (KGE; 0.09 - 0.11) and other GPDs (PERSIANN-CDR, PERSIANN-CCS, IMERGHHFv06) present low performance comparatively. In the hydrologic modeling evaluation, all GPDs show a good performance in generating streamflow when the model is calibrated by each GPD separately. Among gauge corrected GPDs, CHIRPSv2.0 performs better and more stable compared to IMERGHHFv06 and PERSIANN-CDR in all conditions; for gauge uncorrected GPDs, CHIRPv2.0 and IMERGHHLv06 are able to achieve better performance in streamflow prediction compared to PERSIANN-CCS.

Keywords: *Gridded Precipitation Datasets; Reliability; Hydrologic modeling; Mountainous basin; Turkey.*

1 Introduction

Water resources management over mountainous basins is always a key challenge for hydrologists and decision makers due to lack of observed data such as precipitation (Behrangi et al., 2011). On the other hand, remote sensing makes a major contribution to water resources management and development in the last few years (Hafizi and Kalkan, 2020). Moreover, the rapid development of remote sensing techniques provides an outstanding opportunity of using Passive Microwave (PMW) and Infrared (IR) satellite sensor information to come up with high spatial and temporal precipitation estimates (Salmani-Dehaghi and Samani, 2021). In the same way, precipitation from numerical weather prediction model outputs could be an alternative for filling the

lack of observed data over complex terrain (Jiang et al., 2021). Hence, for reliable precipitation estimates, Gridded Precipitation Datasets (GPDs) use either a single source of information into their retrospective algorithms such as Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) late run (L) (Huffman et al., 2020) and Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) Cloud Classification System (CCS) (Hong et al., 2004) or including information from multi sources such as Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation (CHIRP) with Stations (CHIRPS) (Funk et al., 2015), Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) final run (F) (Huffman et al., 2020) and Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) Climate Data Record (CDR) (Ashouri et al., 2015). Generally, GPDs are classified as gauge uncorrected (temporal variation does not depend on ground observations) or gauge corrected (temporal variation entirely or partially depend on ground observations) (Beck et al., 2019). Moreover, two types of validation efforts are used by several authors whereby GPDs are evaluated either by direct comparison with gauge precipitation network or using them as a meteorological forcing in hydrologic models for reproducing streamflow (Bitew and Gebremichael, 2011). Moreover, the performance of some GPDs over Turkey have been quantified by several authors (Aksu and Akgül, 2020; Amjad et al., 2020; Derin and Yilmaz, 2014; Irvem and Ozbuldu, 2019). However, in these studies either meteorological part is only evaluated or recent GPDs have not been validated. Moreover, GPDs are evaluated over an entire period where seasonal variability of precipitation is not taken into account. Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to evaluate the consistency of recent six GPDs (CHIRPSv2.0, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv06, IMERGHHL v06, PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS) over time and space by considering seasonal variability of precipitation and the strength of GPDs for streamflow prediction using hydrologic modeling considering two different scenarios. Section 1 provides a detailed introduction, Section 2 introduces materials and methods of evaluation, Section 3 presents the results/discussion and conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Karasu basin with its elevation ranging from 1130m to 3500m, is one of the major tributaries of the Euphrates River which is known as the longest transboundary river in southwest Asia and the largest river basin (127.3×10^3 Km²) in Turkey. Karasu basin, situated within 38° 58' E to 41° 39' E and 39° 23' N to 40° 25' N in the eastern part of Turkey has a drainage area of 10250 km² and is controlled by Kemah Boğazı (E21A019) stream gaging station (Figure 1). Moreover, as a result of terrain complexity in the eastern part of the country, the basin receives precipitation in both snow and rain forms while precipitation in the form of snow contribute to streamflow once the temperatures rise over the region. Furthermore, Karasu is a pilot basin which contributes to multi-national and many international scientific projects. Hence, evaluation of spatial and temporal stability and hydrologic response of different GPDs for streamflow simulation over Karasu river basin is crucial (Uysal et al., 2016).

Figure 1. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and distributed hydrometeorological stations in the study area.

2.2 Hydro-Meteorological Data

In this context, daily observed precipitation and temperature data from 23 station are provided by General Directorate of Meteorology (GDM) of Turkey and the observed discharge data of Kemah Boğazı (E21A019) stream gaging station is obtained from General Directorate of Hydraulic Works (GDH) in Turkey for the period of October 2014 to September 2019.

In this study, daily-based precipitation data are obtained from six GPDs namely Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) v2.0 and Climate Hazards group InfraRed Precipitation (CHIRP) v2.0 (Funk et al., 2015), Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) final run v06, Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) late run v06 (Huffman et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2016), Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) Climate Data Record (CDR) and Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) Cloud Classification System (CCS) (Adler et al., 2003; Ashouri et al., 2015).

2.3 Evaluation approach

The quantitative analysis of all GPDs is done based on the Kling Gupta Efficiency (Gupta et al., 2009; Kling et al., 2012) which combine correlation coefficient (R), ratio of bias (β) and variability ratio (VR). Moreover, three categorical indices such as Probability of Detection (POD), False Alarm Ratio (FAR) and Critical Success Index (CSI) are used to evaluate the detectability strength of each GPD for different precipitation events, and the selected categorical indices are used in many studies (Kim and Han, 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019). In the same way, Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE) are selected to analyze the hydrologic utility of six GPDs for streamflow prediction. Table 1 shows the detailed information on performance metrics which are used in this study. Furthermore, based on World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2008) standard for precipitation events and its modification by Zambrano-Bigiarini (Zambrano-Bigiarini et al., 2017); daily precipitation events from observed and six GPDs are classified into five thresholds (0-1, 1-5, 5-20, 20-40 and ≥ 40 mm/day) which are indicated as no-precipitation, light, moderate, heavy and violent precipitation respectively. Hence, to compare GPDs with observed data, the value of each grid of GPD at the station locations are extracted (Chua et al., 2020).

Table 1. Summary of performance metrics selected for GPD evaluation

Performance indicator	Mathematical statement	Best value	Explanation
Kling Gupta Efficiency	$KGE=1-[(R-1)^2+(\beta-1)^2+(VR-1)^2]^{0.5}$	1	$R=\frac{1}{n}\sum_1^n(o_n - \mu_o)(s_n \mu_s)/(\delta_o \times \delta_s)$, $\beta=\frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o}$, $VR=(\delta_s \times \mu_o)/(\mu_s \times \delta_o)$
Probability of Detection	$POD=\frac{Hit}{(Hit+Miss)}$	1	R is the Pearson correlation coefficient. β (<i>Bias</i>) is the ratio of estimated and observed means. VR (<i>Variability ratio</i>) is the ratio of estimated and observed coefficients of variation μ and δ are the distribution mean and standard deviation where s and o indicate estimate and observed. <i>Miss</i> when the observed precipitation is not detected. <i>False</i> when the precipitation is detected but not observed. <i>Hit</i> when the observed precipitation is correctly detected. n is the sample size of the observed or calculated streamflow time series. Q_i^o and Q_i^s present the observed and simulated streamflow time series. \overline{Q}_t^o present the mean observed streamflow.
False Alarm Ratio	$FAR=\frac{False}{(Hit+False)}$	0	
Critical Success Index	$CSI=\frac{Hit}{Hit+False+Miss}$	1	
Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency	$NSE=1-\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^s - Q_i^o)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^o - \overline{Q}_t^o)^2}$	1	

2.4 Hydrologic model

The TUW model, developed by Technical University of Vienna, is a lumped, conceptual hydrologic model used for streamflow prediction (Viglione and Parajka, 2019). The model has been tested with good performance over different locations and basin scales in literature (Neri et al., 2020; Parajka et al., 2007; Viglione and Parajka, 2019). TUW model follows the structure of the well-known HBV model (Bergstrom, 1995; Bergström & Lindström, 2015) which operates in daily time step. It has 15 model parameters (Table 2) and is able to simulate snow, soil moisture and runoff routines (Parajka et al., 2007).

Hydrologic utility of GPDs is evaluated based-on the following two scenarios; 1. The hydrologic model is calibrated with observed precipitation and then replaced by GPDs (Scheme-1). 2. The hydrologic model is calibrated by each GPD individually (Scheme-2) as if modeling an ungagged basin (S. Jiang et al., 2012; Xue et al., 2013).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Continuous and Categorical Performances of GPDs

Figure 2 shows the median Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE) including its three components (R, Bias and VR) and the mean of categorical metrics (POD, FAR and CSI) using five different daily precipitation intensities for the selected GPDs over the study area considering entire period and seasonal variability. CHIRPSv2.0 shows the highest performance (KGE; 0.15) compared to other GPDs through the entire period while it performs lowest in summer (KGE; 0.03) and highest in winter (KGE; 0.14) in terms of seasonality. Furthermore, CHIRPSv2.0 overestimates bias and underestimates variability ratio and its correlation varies from 0.07 to 0.30 for the entire period and four seasons. On the other hand, CHIRPv2.0 displays a lower performance in terms of KGE showing a better correlation but a significant underestimation of variability ratio for all conditions. IMERGHFv06 presents a low KGE performance with a considerable bias overestimate (Bias; 2.14) especially during the winter season.

Figure 2. Gridded precipitation reliability at the regional scale considering entire period and four seasons. IMERGHHLv06 comes with the second-best performance during the entire period compared to other GPDs and its performance through the summer (KGE; 0.06) and autumn (KGE; 0.17) places this dataset in first rank while it is the only dataset which underestimates bias in the spring and autumn seasons. Finally, both PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS perform low throughout the entire period and four seasons. Although, PERSIANN-CDR shows a better correlation compared to PERSIANN-CCS, they both display the highest bias overestimates for the winter season.

Generally, all GPDs accurately detect precipitation less than 1 mm/day for the entire period and all seasons which is reflected by higher probability of detection (POD), relatively lower false alarm ratio (FAR) and higher critical success index (CSI). Furthermore, GPD detectability decreases by the increasing precipitation intensities and they are weak in capturing heavy and violent precipitation events. CHIRPSv2.0 is the only GPD showing high detectability of moderate precipitation compared to light precipitation events where CHIRPv2.0 detects light precipitation more precisely. In the same way, both IMERGHHFv06 and IMERGHHLv06 show higher detectability for no-precipitation, light and moderate precipitation considering the entire period and four seasons while their strength for capturing heavy and violent precipitation decreases, comparatively. On the other hand, PERSIANN-CDR presents higher detectability of light and moderate precipitation while PERSIANN-CCS is able to better capture less than 1mm/day and heavy precipitation events. Both PERSIANN products show weak detectability for violent precipitation events over the entire period and for each season.

3.2 Evaluation of Daily Streamflow Simulation

Precipitation data from observed gauges and six selected GPDs are used as meteorological forcing in TUW model for performing daily streamflow simulation over Karasu basin. The simulation is performed for 5 water years from October 2014 to September 2019 where the observed data are classified into model calibration (October 2014 to September 2016) and validation (October 2016 to September 2019). The model parameters are first calibrated using observed gauge precipitation and then replaced by GPDs (scheme-1, Figure 4.). Secondly, TUW model parameters are calibrated based on each GPD individually (scheme-2, Figure 4). Overall, all GPDs produce streamflow well when the model is calibrated by each GPD separately, generally showing higher accuracy during calibration period.

Figure 3. Hydrograph of observed and simulated streamflow from gauges and six GPDs.

CHIRPSv2.0 and CHIRPv2.0 are the only GPDs which show better reproducibility of streamflow simulation both for scheme-1 and scheme-2. Meanwhile, IMERGHHLv06 is able to reproduce streamflow close to the observed in scheme-1 compared to its gauge corrected dataset (IMERGHHFv06) and IMERGHHFv06 shows more overestimation of streamflow, comparatively. Moreover, both IMERGHHv06 products present better reproducibility of streamflow for scheme-2 compared to scheme-1. As for the PERSIANN products (PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS), they have a low performance in representing streamflow whereby drastically overestimating the volume in scheme-1. PERSIANN-CDR is able to reproduce streamflow better compared to PERSIANN-CCS considering scheme-2. However, PERSIANN-CCS is the only GPD not able to replicate observed streamflow in both schemes exhibiting high overestimates.

Figure 5 summarizes the performance of daily streamflow simulation for observed precipitation and selected GPDs at Karasu basin outlet (E21A019) considering two schemes for calibration (October 2014 to September

2016), validation (October 2016 to September 2019) and entire 5 water years. The KGE with its correlation, bias and variability ratio components as well as Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) is used to address the performance of GPDs for streamflow. Generally, using gauge precipitation as a model input for streamflow simulation presents the highest performance measured by NSE (0.84), KGE (0.92) and its correlation (0.92), bias (0.99) and

Figure 4. Performance of daily streamflow for observed precipitation and selected GPDs

variability ratio (0.99) components for the calibration period. Observed precipitation shows slightly lower performance for the validation period which is usually expected. Among all GPDs, CHIRPSv2.0 and CHIRPv2.0 show higher performance for both schemes while IMERGHHLv06 comes in third place. IMERGHHFv06 performs poorly in scheme-1 but displays a better simulation in scheme-2. Moreover, PERSIANN-CDR shows higher NSE and KGE for scheme-2 compared to scheme-1, while PERSIANN-CCS performs poorly for both scenarios, respectively. In scheme-1, PERSIANN-CDR overestimates bias significantly followed by PERSIANN-CCS and IMERGHHFv06 for the calibration period while for the validation period, PERSIANN-

Table 2. Optimum model parameters for observed and six GPDs, the number of the columns indicates; 1, Obs; 2, CHIRPSv2.0; 3, CHIRPv2.0; 4, IMERGHHFv06; 5, IMERGHHLv06; 6, PERSIANN-CDR; 7, PERSIANN-CCS.

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Snow correction factor - (-)	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.0	1.3	0.9	0.9
Degree-day factor - (mm/°C /day)	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.8	4.0
Temperature threshold above which precipitation is rain - (°C)	2.5	2.9	2.6	1.4	2.5	2.4	1.7
Temperature threshold below which precipitation is snow - (°C)	-1.0	-1.7	0.1	-0.1	-2.4	-2.5	-2.0
Temperature threshold above which melt starts - (°C)	-0.5	1.0	1.6	0.8	-0.1	1.0	-1.0
Parameter related to the limit for potential evaporation - (-)	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.9	0.6	0.7
Field capacity - (mm)	132	135	146	45	61	575	543
Non-linear parameter for runoff production - (-)	0.9	1.0	0.9	5.5	1.2	1.8	2.4
Constant percolation rate - (mm/day)	0.6	0.	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.8	1.3
Storage coefficient for very fast response - (day)	26.3	20.0	26.4	20.0	19.6	25.8	26.7
Storage coefficient for fast response - (day)	36.1	31.4	31.6	50.9	39.0	47.8	55.2
Storage coefficient for slow response - (day)	51.8	74.0	73.8	57.5	61.9	58.7	43.2
Threshold storage state - (mm)	6.4	4.4	5.6	6.9	6.0	5.5	4.4
Maximum base at low flows - (day)	14.2	18.4	16.5	7.7	13.5	22.9	13.9
Free scaling parameter - (day ² /mm)	17.8	37.2	33.2	24.3	24.9	30.0	37.5

CCS show higher overestimates of bias, comparatively. Moreover, CHIRPv2.0 underestimates variability ratio in calibration period while PERSIANN-CDR significantly underestimates variability ratio for validation period in scheme-1. For the entire period, three GPDs, IMERGHHFv06, PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS show lower performance and higher overestimation considering scheme-1. PERSIANN-CCS shows poor simulation for scheme-2 where the rest of GPDs display a better performance when compared to scheme-1. Table 2 presents TUW model optimum parameters for scheme-2 calibration by observed precipitation and selected GPDs in reproducing streamflow at Karasu basin outlet.

4 Conclusions

In this context, spatio-temporal and hydrologic utility of six GPDs (CHIRPSv2.0, CHIRPv2.0, IMERGHHFv06, IMERGHHLv06, PERSIANN-CDR and PERSIANN-CCS) are investigated over Karasu river basin considering five hydrologic years (October 2014 to September 2019). The reliability of GPDs are evaluated based on 23 precipitation gauges and one stream gauging station. The KGE including its three components (correlation, bias and variability ratio), NSE and three categorical metrics (POD, FAR, CSI) are selected for meteorological and hydrological evaluation. Important conclusions are summarized below.

- CHIRPSv2.0 and CHIRPv2.0 datasets using information from multi-sources present high performance of precipitation estimates and streamflow reproducibility over time.
- In a mountainous basin, IMERGHHLv06 displays a higher performance of precipitation estimates and streamflow as compared to IMERGHHFv06.
- PERSIANN-CDR shows more stability and better performance of streamflow simulation and precipitation distribution compared to PERSIANN-CCS.
- CHIRPSv2.0 and CHIRPv2.0 are the only GPDs which simulate streamflow close to observed discharge when the model parameters are calibrated by gauge precipitation.
- Overall, all GPDs show better performance for streamflow simulation when the model parameters are calibrated according to individual GPDs.

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